

USE OF PIEZOELECTRIC THICK FILM SENSORS TO MEASURE STRESS DISTRIBUTION WITHIN A JOINT

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Keywords: Piezoelectric, Sensor, Joint, Strain

ABSTRACT

A novel approach of obtaining quantitative, interfacial strength information in adhesively bonded joints is proposed in this work. To achieve this, piezoelectric thick film sensors have been developed to be embedded into the adhesive layer of a lap joint and used as strain sensors. One of the main challenges was to develop a piezoelectric sensor that could be incorporated into the adhesive layer of a lap joint without greatly affecting the joint's mechanical properties. This application allows the direct measurement of the variation of the interfacial strength in a joint along the bond area, aiming at the optimisation of the adhesively bonded joint design. In the present work, the joints were tested using the dynamic four-point bending test and preliminary results demonstrated the feasibility of this approach achieving a satisfactory performance of the piezoelectric sensors within the joint. Due to the dynamic response nature of the piezoelectric sensors, the experimental tests were carried out over a range of cyclic displacement amplitudes, where an increase of the output signal was observed, directly proportional to increases of the applied displacement amplitude. The signals were conditioned using a custom made charge amplifier, with sensitivity equal to 1.0mV/pC, and all experimental data were acquired by a NI 9219 (DAQ) board, using a LabView data logging program. Having established a formulation for setting up a single piezoelectric sensor as an in-service device within a metal to metal joint, work proceeded to the application of several sensors within dissimilar material joints. The assessment of the output signal was compared with results from finite element analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonding is proposed as the most efficient method of joining either similar or dissimilar materials in several structural applications where fusion welding is not possible especially for lightweight structures in aeronautic, rail and automotive applications. In order to investigate the quality of the bond and the poor adhesion in the interface of a lap joint analytical and numerical models have been developed in the past [1]. In the present work an attempt of using a new form of strain sensor, based on piezoelectric material powders, is proposed as an alternative way to investigate the stress distribution along the adhesive layer of a lap joint. There are many applications where piezoelectric materials, in the form of wafers, fibres or macro fibres, are used to form piezoelectric sensors. Practical advantage is their direct application on the surface or embedding into the main structure [2]. The additional advantages of the new type of piezoelectric sensor described in this work can be summarised as follows.

1. It can be part of the adhesive layer of a lap joint without greatly affecting the mechanical properties of the bond.
2. There is no special curing process requirement, as the matrix material of the sensor is the same polymer which is used for the overall adhesive of the joint.
3. It can be applied and used as in-service strain sensor.

Piezoelectricity is the physical property of a material to become electrically polarized when it experiences a mechanical force [3]. This behaviour is labelled as direct piezoelectric effect. Piezoelectric thick-film sensors have been developed and used as stress sensors and displacement actuators, where Newman first introduced the term 'piezoelectric paint'. Later several attempts were made to mix a piezoelectric (PZT) ceramic powder into an acrylic lacquer and form a sprayable piezoelectric paint. The latter application was fully described by Hale and Tuck [4].

The objective of the current study was the development of a unique form of piezoelectric sensor, embedded within the adhesive layer of a joint. The main focus laid on the application of the sensor in order to provide quantitative data of the stress distribution along the bond line of an adhesively bonded joint in order to assess its service performance. The four-point bending (4PB) test setup, which was proposed by Poizat and Thielicke [5] as simple but highly effective method, is used to investigate the sensor functionality.

2 PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE DEVELOPMENT

For many years quartz and tourmaline were the most popular natural minerals with piezoelectric properties. Nowadays there are several materials exhibiting piezoelectric properties that are mostly artificial materials made of metallic oxides. The most commonly used piezoelectric material is Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT) with molecular formula $Pb(Zr_x Ti_{1-x})O_3$. Similar structure and use have the Lead Scandium Tantalite and the Barium Strontium Titanate, which are also used as active materials in strain sensors. Usually a piezoelectric material has a perovskite structure or tungsten – bronze structure. Under conditions above or below Curie temperature (where the Curie temperature is the temperature where a material's permanent magnetism changes to induced magnetism) this crystalline structure has tetragonal or rhombohedral symmetry and become an electric dipole. In addition the ceramic element needs to be exposed to a strong electric field to be polarized prior to use. When the electric field is removed the majority of the dipoles are stabilized into this configuration of almost perfect alignment with respect to the orientation of the applied electric field.

By mixing a piezoelectric material with a liquid it is possible to create a piezoelectric sensor that can be applied to almost any surface and monitor the stress distribution of a structure. The first piezoelectric sensors were developed by Newham in the 1980's and then Hale and his co-workers investigated piezoelectric sensors using water-based acrylic resin [6, 7]. In this case the active component, the piezoelectric ceramic powder, was dispersed in a passive matrix, which bound the composite together and formed the sensor. After testing several ceramic materials and different ways of manufacturing, researchers concluded that the main parameters that affect the sensitivity of a piezoelectric sensor are the thickness of the sensor, the poling field in which the sensor is exposed prior to its use and the poling time that the poling field is applied [8]. However, the unique physical properties of the material being used as the pigment and the binder have a major role regarding the functionality of the sensor.

The most common type of piezoelectric composite is known as a 0-3 composite. The classification of the PZT composites is given according to the connectivity of piezoelectric ceramics and matrix phases. The first number denotes the connectivity of the ceramics phase, and the second refers to that of the matrix. The '0' means that the active component has no connectivity in any direction, where the matrix, the passive component, has connectivity in all three directions, meaning that the piezoelectric particles are isolated from one another in a continuous matrix. According to the literature thick piezoelectric films are in a range of 10-500 μ m thick, where thin films are considered to have thickness less than 1 μ m [9].

In the current work a unique form of piezoelectric strain sensor is developed, being termed 'piezoelectric adhesive', using PZT as piezoelectric material, epoxy resin as matrix and tailored to be embedded into the joint. Figure 1 shows the configuration of the piezoelectric sensor which was used for the evaluation of the paint.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Test Method

Techniques were developed in this work for making a piezoelectric thick-film material using PZT powder as the active ingredient and epoxy resin as the matrix. Dynamic strain sensors were manufactured using this material and preferred parameters (PZT type and proportion, poling time and voltage) were identified. A simple test rig was used to load the beam dynamically and controllably in 4 point bending (4PB) to induce a known strain in the sensors and the output signal was captured on a digital oscilloscope. This test method was also used to enable comparison with previous work on acrylic matrix sensors. Figure 1 shows the general layout of the experimental set up which was used for the evaluation of the piezoelectric thick-film sensor.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of a piezoelectric thick-film sensor (film thicknesses are exaggerated for clarity)

The experimental procedure revolved round two parts: a) development of a suitable composition of sensor and b) a method for embedding the sensors into the joints. The evaluation of the piezoelectric composite involved an assessment of the main parameters influencing the electrical response of the sensor and the behaviour of the sensor under dynamic loading, as piezoelectric strain sensors are inherently dynamic. The work then progressed into making sensors embedded within the adhesive layer of metal to metal joints in an attempt to provide quantitative data of the load distribution along the bond. In this case, the important characteristic to be determined for the case of a single sensor was the consistency of response over the operating displacement amplitude. Dissimilar material joints were then manufactured where three identical sensors were deposited into the adhesive layer of the bond. Dynamic 4PB tests were carried out to investigate the sensitivity of the PZT sensors in both cases, using a computer controlled screw type universal testing machine (Shimadzu AGS-X series) at a range of displacement amplitudes. The sensor signals were conditioned using a custom-made charge amplifier with sensitivity of 1.0mV/pC and the experimental data were acquired by a NI 9219 (DAQ) board using a LabView data logging program.

3.2 Sample preparation

Two different PZT powders were tested in three different weight fractions. The powders were nominally the same specification of “soft” PZT, commonly known as Navy type II, from two manufacturers. The two ceramic powders were PZ 27 produced by Ferroperm Piezoceramics A/S and PZT 5A produced by Sunytec Electronics CO. Ltd. The ceramic particles were in the form of fine particles with significantly different degrees of agglomeration. More specifically, PZ27 had a coarser appearance than PZT 5A. Two types of epoxy resin, TechnoWrap 2K and RS-L135, were chosen for manufacturing the composite. Three different weight fractions of the piezoelectric composite were prepared with loadings of 50, 70 and 90 wt% and dispersed by using ultrasonic bath. The ultrasonic bath dispersion procedure lasted from 15min to 30min according to the concentration of each mixture, with regular breaks where hand mixing took place. Trials were done on sensors deposited onto a free surface of a thin steel beam.

The piezoelectric composite was applied onto the steel beams using a laboratory steel cylinder applicator which had a fixed gap, allowing precise control of the film thickness. To make a modular probe, a 15mm×150mm steel strip was selected as a base, where the piezoelectric thick film sensor

was deposited. A narrow film strip of conductive paint was then applied onto the piezoelectric composite, specifying the active area of the sensor and forming the second electrode of the sensor. The standard sensor area for these tests was 12mm×25mm.

Signal wires were connected to the electrodes by soldering onto small patches of self-adhesive copper shim. The final step in manufacture was ‘poling’, which activates the piezoelectric sensor by aligning the electric dipoles within the crystal lattice of the PZT particles. These changes in orientation exaggerated the response and made the visualization easier. The sensors were subjected to a voltage range up to 1500V for a period of 2-10min at room temperature.

Joints were prepared using the optimum piezoelectric composite formulation which was determined after the sensor evaluation stage. A mixture 70 wt% ceramic powder PZT 5A was prepared using the RS-L135 epoxy resin as binder. The surface to surface bonding using the piezoelectric composite covered a limited area of the adhesive layer and forming a single PZT sensor, leaving the rest covered by pure epoxy. The area of the single sensor was specified by the numerical analysis prior to the application of the sensor (Figure 2). The main purpose of the numerical analysis was to identify where the main stress concentrations would be located so that the sensors could be placed in this area, expecting that they would provide the best output signal. The joints were tested under dynamic 4PB loading after curing was complete. Work proceeded by assessing the behaviour of the single sensor under a range of applied dynamic loads.

Figure 2: FE stress analysis showing elastic strain distribution of a joint under 4PB loading

The following step in this study was the manufacture of dissimilar material joints, where several PZT sensors were embedded into the adhesive layer along the bondline. In this case metal to glass fibre reinforced laminate (GFRP) joints were prepared, where three piezoelectric sensors were inserted at intervals along the bondline to work as strain sensors. The main challenge of this attempt was the application of the second essential electrode of the PZT sensor on the nonconductive GFRP substrate. Nickel spray was used to deposit three identical conductive patches on the composite substrate, where a self-adhesive copper shim assisted in the extraction of the electrode out of the bond (Figure 3). The samples were cured according to the curing specifications of the epoxy resin, poled as previously and tested under dynamic 4PB at displacement amplitude of 0.4mm. The results were compared with the FEA simulation.

Figure 3: Top view of the GFRP substrate, where the three identical conductive films have been formed using Nickel spray

3.3 Four-point bending setup

Four-point bending (4PB) tests were performed for the characterisation of the proposed piezoelectric adhesive, which induced tensile loading of the PZT sensor. Figure 4 shows the schematic representation of the 4PB test set-up. This test configuration is used by AIRBUS to assess the strength of adhesively bonded joints as it induces high peel stresses at the free ends of the bottom substrate.

Figure 4: Schematic configuration of a single sensor embedded into a joint under 4PB test (film thicknesses are exaggerated for clarity)

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The different compositions of piezoelectric adhesive were first evaluated using a custom test rig, where a dead weight loading was employed and no force measurement was required. For 4PB loading the bending stress was uniform along the steel beam, where the piezoelectric adhesive has been applied, and hence the strain was uniform within the sensor film. The piezoelectric adhesive sensor signals were measured using a digital oscilloscope and a charge amplifier. The typical trace of the output signal is shown in Figure 5. For step loading and unloading of the steel beam the output signal had the form of an impulse with a time delay in between, which was due to the characteristic response of the piezoelectric material.

Figure 5: Sensor signal obtained using digital oscilloscope

As mentioned earlier, trials were made using two different piezoelectric ceramics and initial results showed that the best performing was the PZT 5A ceramic powder. Figure 6 shows the output signal for the different composition of piezoelectric adhesive using PZT 5A. Generally, the sensors using RS-L135 epoxy resin as binder perform better than the sensors manufactured, using the TechnoWrap 2K resin. Preferred compositions were compared, proposing 70 wt% PZT 5A - RS-L135 as the sensor with the highest sensitivity, which was labelled as the optimum formulation.

Figure 6: Probe signal as a function of the different compositions and epoxy resins

Work continued with attempts to embed the piezoelectric sensors into the adhesive layer of a joint. Initially, three metal to metal joints were manufactured, where the two metal substrates were used as the two essential electrodes of the sensor and tested under 4PB. Figure 7 shows the output signal and

the standard deviation for the three sensors, which were tested six times under the same loading. The output signal showed good repeatability of the response over load, allowing the work to continue into the characterisation tests of the sensor as shown in Figure 8. The dynamic characterization of the piezoelectric adhesive was carried out using a high-control strength machine, where the displacement amplitude limits were imposed by the specifications of the sample so the process did not lead to failure of the sample. The output signal was measured and logged using the LabView software.

Figure 7: Consistency of the sensor's response

In Figure 8 the output signal from the PZT sensor is presented as a function of the applied displacement amplitude. This shows the increase of the output signal as the applied amplitude increases.

Figure 8: Dynamic characterisation of the piezoelectric sensor

Attempts to embed more than a single sensor into the adhesive layer of a joint followed the sensor

assessment. For this case dissimilar material joints were manufactured and tested under 4PB at displacement amplitude of 0.4mm (Figure 9). The objective was to fully characterise the performance of the piezoelectric adhesive, embedded into joints, and give a relative sensitivity in accordance with FE modelling.

Figure 9: Schematic configuration of the three PZT sensors (S1, S2, and S3) embedded into a joint under 4PB test (film thicknesses are exaggerated for clarity and half of the sample is presented)

5 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION AND RESULTS

A finite element analysis was carried out in-line with Goland and Reissner’s work, where the joint was treated as being in plain strain [10]. A parametric 2D model of the 4PB test was formed to simulate the experimental set up. This method assisted with the interpretation of experimental results from the PZT sensors and provided prediction of the sensors performance. In Figure 10 the output signal for the three PZT sensors embedded into the adhesive layer of the joint is presented along with the elastic strain (%) as it was derived by the FE analysis of the joint.

Figure 10: Sensor performance and FE simulation of 2D model of a joint under 4PB test loading

In the analysis ANSYS APDL 14.5 PLANE183 2D 8-Node structural elements were used to build the geometry, where due to symmetry only half of the joint was modelled. The finite element model was divided in three different areas, the upper adherent, the adhesive layer and the bottom adherent,

where the mesh resolution was the same in all areas. However the mesh was refined enough to capture the strain values near the overlap corner. At this stage it was thought that a detailed analysis with a finely refined mesh at the overlap corner was not necessary. The influence of joint design parameters such as the type of the joint, geometry and material properties were under investigation.

In order to assess the PZT sensor performance within the joint, the numerical analysis continued with an extensive parametric study of the strain developed under static loading. As such, mechanical validation tests of the joint were performed where strain gauges were placed at the outer surface of the joint substrate and the results were compared to the numerical output and the analytical results (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Strain gauges configuration

6 CONCLUSION

In this work a type of novel piezoelectric film sensor was developed using PZT powder and epoxy resin that could be embedded into an adhesively bonded joint to provide quantitative data of stress distribution along the bondline, as well as serve as an in-service condition monitoring device.

The results have shown that a 70% loading of PZT powder in an RS L135 epoxy resin produces the best signal output. Results of tests on both similar and dissimilar material joints, based on 4PB tests, have shown a very good correlation with analytical results providing confidence in the performance of the sensors. For dissimilar material joints in particular, the fact that the epoxy resin used as the matrix for the sensors can also be the same as the matrix of the composite laminate forming the joint, is a major advantage of the technique and ensures the sensor film has a minimum influence in the load carrying capacity of the joint.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial support by EU in the project 'SAFEJOINT' is gratefully acknowledged as well as the valuable dedication of several colleagues at the School of Mechanical and Systems Engineering Department at Newcastle University

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